

Novel strategy for combustion enhancement of NH₃-air mixture using gliding arc plasma

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of gliding arc plasma (GAP) on the stability and emissions characteristics of a partially premixed ammonia (NH₃)-air swirling flames for wide ranges of global equivalence ratios (ϕ_g). A novel dual-swirl GAP combustor, incorporating conical central electrode serving as a bluff body, is used to generate a rotating gliding arc plasma within the fuel lance. The plasma power is maintained below 1.4 % of the thermal power of the flame across all experimental conditions. This is the first study to apply GAP directly to the fuel side, facilitating premixing immediately after plasma interaction. The results reveal that plasma significantly enhances lean and rich blowout limits by 15–20 % and 30–35 %, respectively. This is mainly due to the continuous local ignition effect through heating and the generation of active species pools. Plasma actuation also results in a substantial reduction in NO and NO₂ emissions, decreasing by 40–80 % and 30–50 %, respectively, depending on ϕ_g in the range of 0.76 to 1.05. Simultaneously, OH* and NH₂* intensities increase by 30–60 % and 70–80 %, respectively. This could indicate an increased NH₂ production favouring NO consumption reactions. A notable NH₃ slip occurs at ϕ_g values exceeding 0.93 and 0.76, indicating incomplete combustion. Numerical results suggest that NO formation predominantly occurs via the HNO pathway, and that plasma conditions promote thermal De-NO_x reactions, notably through NH₂ + NO → NNH + OH and NH₂ + NO → N₂ + H₂O reactions. This study provides critical insights into the potential of GAP technique for advancing NH₃ combustion technologies, offering promising applications for sustainable energy systems.

1. Introduction

Ammonia (NH₃) has gained significant attention as a carbon-free hydrogen carrier and potential alternative fuel in the quest for sustainable energy solutions [1,2]. The high energy density, ease of storage, and well-established production and transportation infrastructure make NH₃ a promising future fuel for various power and transport applications [3]. However, NH₃ combustion faces inherent challenges, including low combustion efficiency, narrow flammability range, and high nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions, which hinder its adoption as a primary fuel source [4].

To enhance the combustion characteristics of NH₃, various approaches have been explored, such as cofiring with reactive fuels [5], staged combustion [6], humidification [7], and plasma-assisted combustion [8] etc. Among them, plasma-assisted combustion has emerged

as a promising solution due to its easy integration with existing combustion systems, requiring minimal modifications while significantly enhancing combustion chemistry [9]. Various non-equilibrium plasmas such as those produced by dielectric barrier discharges (DBD), gliding arcs (GAP), and nanosecond repetitively pulsed (NRP) discharges, have demonstrated remarkable potential to influence combustion chemistry by generating reactive radicals and promoting energy-efficient ignition processes [10,11].

Recently, several experimental and numerical studies on plasma-assisted NH₃ combustion have been reported [8,12–17]. Shioyoke et al. [12] demonstrated that DBD plasma enhances the laminar burning velocity of NH₃ flames by accelerating NH₃ decomposition via OH radical generation. Kim et al. [13] conducted a parametric study to study the effect of plasma on the flammability limit and emissions of premixed NH₃ swirl flames. They found that NH₂* production with plasma

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actuation significantly reduces NO emissions. Faingold and Lefkowitz [14] numerically demonstrated a 40–60 % reduction in ignition delay time for $\text{NH}_3/\text{O}_2/\text{He}$ mixtures using NRP plasmas. Several fundamental studies have also reported on the effect of NRP plasma on NH_3 combustion chemistry [15,17]. Choe et al. [16] experimentally showed that NRP discharges extend lean blowout (LBO) limits while reducing NO_x emissions for NH_3 -air turbulent flames for a specific equivalence ratio. Shohdy et al. [8] compared flame morphology, blowout limits, and emission profiles between thermal cracking and NRP plasma actuation in swirling NH_3 -air flames. They concluded that plasma volume, location, and kinetic effects are critical for designing efficient plasma-assisted NH_3 combustion actuators. Recently, Shah et al. [18] and Radwan and Paul [19] conducted a comprehensive review on plasma assisted NH_3 combustion. They emphasised the need for further research on the impact of plasma on NH_3 and emission reduction kinetics to address the challenges associated with NH_3 usage in practical applications.

The rotating gliding arc plasma offers extensive volume coverage and can be directly integrated into the combustion field, making it highly promising for enhancing combustion [20]. Tang et al. [21] utilised GAP to stabilise NH_3 swirling flames at ultra-lean equivalence ratios, achieving low NO emissions. Sun et al. [22] later applied the same combustor for NH_3 - CH_4 blends, improving flame stability and lowering emissions. Furthermore, Ju et al. [23] conducted a stability analysis, demonstrating that plasma application eliminates flame instability hysteresis observed in the NH_3 -air flames.

Despite these advancements in GAP, most studies have primarily focused on improving flammability limits, with limited emphasis on mitigating NO_x emissions and the mechanism behind its formation. The production of reactive oxygen species, such as OH and O radicals, during plasma actuation often promotes NO formation through the HNO pathway which contributes >70 % of the overall NO_x formation [19,24]. A targeted approach involving NH_2 radical generation via plasma actuation without compromising the OH production could drive the De- NO_x pathway, thereby reducing NO_x emissions [25,26]. However, achieving this requires careful optimisation of combustor design and plasma configuration. One way to achieve this optimisation of plasma actuation, would be to generate the plasma in the NH_3 stream only, and not in the NH_3 -air mixture, like in all previous studies [8,12–17]. Although Wang et al. [25] and Lin et al. [26] attempted a separate NH_3 and air streamwise plasma-assisted combustion, the present study provides offers a completely new plasma approach that allows for NH_3 combustion improvement with negligible plasma power over flame thermal power, while these literature to achieve the same results they used 15–25 % of plasma to flame power ratio. This substantial reduction in power consumption is highly advantageous for practical applications. In addition, Wang et al. [25] primarily compares plasma interaction on emission characteristics (only NO) between air and NH_3 , while Lin et al. [26] focuses on the interaction of plasma in NH_3 -air mixtures, varying premixtures in different streams.

In this study, a novel gliding arc plasma combustor is designed specifically aimed at addressing the dual challenge of improving NH_3 combustion characteristics and mitigating NO_x emissions. The effects of gliding arc plasma are experimentally investigated under varying thermal powers and equivalence ratios.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Experimental setup

The experiments were conducted in a novel plasma assisted dual-swirl combustor developed at the Centre of Excellence on Ammonia Technologies (CEAT), Cardiff University. This new setup is schematised in Fig. 1. Two radial co-swirlers, each with a swirl number of 1.4, are positioned at 125 mm and 40 mm from the dump plane for NH_3 and air, respectively. A cylindrical quartz tube (58 mm inner diameter, 320 mm

Fig. 1. Schematic of the plasma combustor.

height) is placed above the nozzle to create a confined combustion zone. High-precision Alicat mass flow controllers were used to control NH_3 , and air flows, achieving an accuracy of ± 0.5 % within 15–95 % of the full scale. The air flow passes through the annular space between the nozzle and fuel lance with a premixing length of $L_p = 2.5$ mm as illustrated in the inset of Fig. 1.

A high-frequency AC power supply (CTP-2000KA, ACS Materials, USA) was used to generate the rotating gliding arc plasma. The input voltage of the power supply was adjusted to maintain a constant power ratio (plasma power to flame power) across different plasma conditions, while the frequency was fixed at 13 kHz. A conical electrode, composed of a tungsten-steel alloy, is integrated into the fuel lance, which has a diameter of 16 mm. The electrode tip is positioned 3 mm away from the lip of lance (L_d) to facilitate gliding arcs that follow the swirling flow and ensure the complete action only in the fuel lance. However, it is worth noting that the longest arc could also interact with the air in the premixing region. Since the majority of the plasma volume resides within the NH_3 stream, NH_3 decomposition is expected to dominate over air decomposition. In addition, Kong et al. [8] showed that for GAP, the plasma effect diminishes as the arc propagates upstream. Therefore, this plasma interaction with air is neglected in the present study. The central rod, responsible for stabilising the flame, also functions as the high-voltage electrode, while the outer nozzle is grounded. The discharge initiates at the narrowest gap (~ 2 mm) and is carried helically along the center body by the swirling gas until arc quenching occurs. After quenching, the arc reignites at the narrowest gap, repeating the cycle.

The voltage and current waveforms were recorded using a Tektronix P6015 high-voltage probe and a Cybertek HCP 8030 current probe respectively, with data acquisition performed via a Tektronix MSO64B oscilloscope. The chemiluminescence spectrum of the flame was analysed using an AvaSpec-ULS spectrometer, with a UV/visible optical fiber positioned 25 mm above the combustor exit and 100 mm from the centerline. The chemiluminescence images of the flames was captured using three LaVision CCD cameras operating simultaneously at a frequency of 10 Hz. The chemiluminescence signals from OH^* ($\text{A}^2\Sigma^- - \text{X}^2\Pi$ system), NH^* ($\text{A}^3\Pi - \text{X}^3\Sigma^-$ system), and NH_2^* (single peak of the NH_2 α band) were collected using bandpass filters: 309 nm (± 10 nm FWHM), 336 nm (± 10 nm FWHM), and 630 nm (± 10 nm FWHM), respectively [27]. For each test condition, 200 frames were captured using LaVision Davis v10, then time-averaged, background-corrected, and Abel transformed.

The exhaust emissions including NO, N_2O , NO_2 , NH_3 , O_2 , and H_2O were measured at 1 Hz using an Emerson CT5100 quantum cascade laser gas analyser, ensuring ± 1 % repeatability and 0.999 linearity. A 30 mm diameter isokinetic funnel, positioned 15 mm above the quartz tube exit,

was used to collect homogeneous gas samples. To prevent condensation, the sampling line was maintained at 463 K. One hundred twenty samples were taken for each test points and then averaged and normalised to dry 15 % O₂ [28].

2.2. Numerical methodology

To comprehend the underlying mechanism of GAP on the reaction kinetics of NH₃-air flames, numerical simulations were conducted using an integrated ZDPlaskin-Chemkin model. The details of the numerical methodology are provided in the supplementary material Fig. S1. This method is used extensively in theoretical analyses of plasma assisted NH₃ combustion [17,29,30]. The numerical methodology of the present GAP simulation is similar to the work of Crispim et al. [31] and Dong et al. [32]. In this study, a new mechanism suitable for GAP is developed by coupling the plasma mechanism proposed by Mao et al. [29] with the NH₃ combustion mechanism by Alnasif et al. [33]. This mechanism has 78 species and 238 reactions. The model is successfully validated against experimental NO emission data for various ϕ_g as shown in Fig. S2 of the supplementary material. This simulation considers the characteristic curves of the current and voltage of the arc, as initial reduced electron field (E/N) and electron density inputs (Ne) to obtain the kinetic changes with gliding arc.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Combustor stability map without plasma

The combustor stability map was analysed across a range of air flow rates (Q_{air}) from 50 SLPM to 250 SLPM, at varying fuel flow rates (Q_{NH_3}) from 24 SLPM to 36 SLPM, with increments of 0.5 SLPM. This corresponds to a thermal power range of 5.3 kW to 7.9 kW.

Several distinct flame morphologies could be observed, including stable flames (S), continuous transitions from stable to tubular flames (ST), attached tubular flames (AT), oscillating tubular flames (OT), and fully detached flames (D), as illustrated in Fig. 2. The characteristic orange hue of NH₃ flames is attributed to the emission of the NH₂ α -band and H₂O vapor spectra [34]. The transition between different flame structures ranging from stable and conical to fully detached is primarily governed by the interplay between flame propagation speed and mixture velocity. Similar flame behaviours have been reported in studies on premixed NH₃ combustion [8,35]. Additionally, the NH₃ flame appears to occupy 80–90 % of the combustion chamber volume, indicating an extensive spread.

Using these flame morphology definitions, the stability map of the combustor is presented in Fig. 3. Each color corresponds to a different

Fig. 2. Different flame morphology observed for different Q_{air} at constant $Q_{NH_3} = 28.5$ SLPM.

Fig. 3. Stability map of the combustor.

flame morphology, and the peach color labelled BO corresponds to conditions at which the flame was blown-out. This stability map includes isolines that delineate the global equivalence ratio (ϕ_g) [36]. Attached 'V'-shaped stable flames are observed for ϕ_g ranging from 0.75 to 1.08, irrespective of the Q_{NH_3} . For $\phi_g > 1.08$, the flame stabilises in two different modes, depending on Q_{NH_3} . Specifically, for $Q_{NH_3} < 28$ SLPM, a hysteresis phenomenon occurs, where the flame alternates between a stable V-shaped structure (S) and a tubular shape (ST), before detaching (D) from the combustor as Q_{air} increases, ultimately leading to rich blowout. Conversely, for $Q_{NH_3} \geq 28$ SLPM, the flame transitions directly from a tubular regime (AT) to a detached state before reaching rich blowout (BO).

For $\phi_g < 0.75$, the flame predominantly adopts a tubular structure that oscillates axially above the combustor lip (OT). A further increase in Q_{air} results in lean blowout (BO), occurring up to $Q_{NH_3} = 31$ SLPM. When $Q_{NH_3} > 31$ SLPM, the flame first stabilises in a tubular regime before transitioning into an oscillating tubular structure and eventually leads to BO. These instability transitions, observed in both lean and rich combustion regimes, can be attributed to the complex interplay between NH₃ slip, heat loss, and wall interactions, which collectively influence thermal power variations with increasing Q_{NH_3} . To better understand the flame stability limit, experimental Damköhler number (Da) is estimated using $Da = \tau_{res} / \tau_{chem}$ [37]. The flow time scale (τ_{res}), is calculated as the ratio of the reactor characteristic length to the axial flow velocity. Whilst the chemical reaction time scale (τ_{chem}), is obtained in a flame as the ratio of the flame thickness to the turbulence flame speed. The characteristic length of the combustor is approximately 200 mm, which corresponds to the main reaction zone of the flame in comparison to the total combustion chamber length of 320 mm. The axial velocity at the combustor exit is obtained from hot wire anemometer measurements under cold flow conditions. Flame thickness is estimated from flame chemiluminescence images, while the turbulent flame speed is approximated using the laminar flame speed of the NH₃-air mixture. The calculated Da values indicate that stable flames exhibit $Da \gg 1$ with typical values around $Da \sim 2$ for fully stable regimes and $Da \sim 1.2$ for attached tubular flame regimes. In contrast, Da falls below unity for all other unstable conditions. This transition in Da is consistent with prior studies [37,38], reinforcing the interpretation that instabilities are promoted when the chemical time scale approaches or exceeds the flow time scale.

3.2. Combustion characteristics with plasma

3.2.1. Flame stability

To ensure a fair comparison of the flame stability limits with plasma across different operating conditions, the power ratio between plasma

and flame is maintained at 1.4 % across all cases by adjusting the input voltage. Unlike conventional GAP systems, where plasma power is distributed across the premixed fuel-air mixture, the applied plasma in this study predominantly interacts with NH_3 , facilitating its intense breakdown. However, a portion of the plasma also interacts with the air within the 2.5 mm premixing region, just below the flame root.

An example of the temporal evolution of voltage and current over 100 ms is shown in Fig. 4(a). The moment of breakdown is typically marked by a peak in current, while the voltage decreases rapidly. Both voltage and current exhibit periodic variations, with each cycle lasting approximately 10 ms. Fig. 4(b) presents the voltage-current waveforms from the highlighted box in Fig. 4(a), covering a duration of 1 ms. During this period, the maximum breakdown current reaches approximately 4.3 A, whereas the current in subsequent cycles after breakdown does not exceed 0.15 A. The maximum voltage is 6.5 kV, occurring slightly earlier than the peak current. Integration of these curves yield an average input power of approximately 96 W for this segment.

Fig. 5 presents the effect of GAP on the lean blow-out (LBO) and rich blow-out (RBO) limits of the combustor. The image inserts show the flame shape just before BO with and without GAP. Flame instabilities observed during the stability map study (Section 3.1) disappear when plasma is applied. This stabilising effect can be explained by a continuous local ignition through heating and generation of active species produced by the discharges. Note that the flames that were V-shaped even with the plasma are considered as blown-out. Without plasma, the flames were tubular, whereas plasma application transformed them into stable V-shaped flames, on both the lean and rich sides. The estimated Da also reflects the BO improvements achieved with plasma. For instance, at $Q_{\text{NH}_3} = 28.5$ SLPM, Da increased from 1.9 at $\phi_g = 1.05$ in the no plasma case to 6.25 with plasma actuation.

The plasma significantly influences the LBO and RBO limits, with enhancements of approximately 15–20 % and 35 %, respectively. This increased stability is primarily attributed to the thermal and kinetic effects of plasma, which facilitate repetitive local ignition. Indeed, the NH_3 decomposition through electron impact reactions associated with thermal heating could initiate the oxidation reactions, inducing the formation of OH, H, O, and NH_x species that enhance combustion chemistry.

To further investigate the impact of plasma on combustion

Fig. 4. (a) and (b). Temporal evolution voltage and current for $Q_{\text{NH}_3} = 28.5$ SLPM for $\phi_g = 0.8$.

Fig. 5. Effect of plasma on the flame stability.

characteristics, chemiluminescence imaging was performed. Fig. 6 shows the Abel-deconvoluted OH^* , NH^* , and NH_2^* chemi-luminescence images at $\phi_g = 0.8$ and $Q_{\text{NH}_3} = 28.5$ SLPM. The flame structures remain similar but exhibit a slight increase in the overall flame length. A significant enhancement in OH^* , NH^* , and NH_2^* intensity is observed with plasma, promoting flame stabilisation. This stabilisation can be attributed to the increase in active species along the shear layer, causing the flame to reattach to the wall, when GAP was used.

3.2.2. Emissions

The emission profiles of NO, NO_2 , N_2O , and NH_3 were measured over a range of ϕ_g from 0.7 to 1.1 at a fixed Q_{NH_3} of 28.5 SLPM as shown in Fig. 7. All concentrations are normalised to a dry oxygen level of 15 % [28]. For brevity, results for other NH_3 flow rates are not presented, as they follow similar trends to those observed for $Q_{\text{NH}_3} = 28.5$ SLPM. The emission measurements were not performed at conditions where the flame exhibited tubular instability and morphological variations (see Figs. 2 and 3). Under no-plasma conditions, NO and NO_2 exhibit a steep increase toward the lean side, with maximum values of 2980 ppm and 150 ppm, respectively, at $\phi_g = 0.8$. This is mainly due to the presence of abundance of OH radicals that promotes the NO production through HNO route [39].

A significant reduction in NO and NO_2 concentrations is observed with plasma actuation for all the ϕ_g investigated. The trends of NO and NO_2 concentrations with plasma closely follow those of no-plasma cases until $\phi_g = 0.8$. However, beyond this point, NO and NO_2 emission decrease drastically, reaching near-zero levels at $\phi_g = 0.7$. The maximum reductions achieved are 40–80 % and 30–50 % respectively for NO and NO_2 , depending on ϕ_g in the range of 0.76 to 1.05. This reduction might be attributed to an enhanced production of NH_2 , as suggested by the chemiluminescence spectral intensity of NH_2^* [39]. Fig. 8 shows the variation of plasma enhancement intensities of OH^* ,

Fig. 6. Abel-deconvoluted OH^* , NH^* and NH_2^* chemiluminescence images at $\phi_g = 0.8$ and $Q_{\text{NH}_3} = 28.5$ SLPM. (Purple colour shows the block to avoid the intense light from the plasma to the intensifier).

Fig. 7. Effects of plasma on pollutant emissions for different global equivalence ratios.

Fig. 8. Percentage enhancement of OH^* , NH^* and NH_2^* chemiluminescence spectral intensity with plasma for different global equivalence ratios.

NH^* and NH_2^* with different ϕ_g where the plasma enhancement is defined as the difference in chemiluminescence intensity between the plasma and no plasma cases, normalised by the chemiluminescence intensity in the respective no plasma case.

It can be seen from Fig. 8 that plasma enhancement of OH^* chemiluminescence intensity decreases with increase in ϕ_g . The OH^* intensity is found to peak at a ϕ_g between 0.8 and 0.85, and decreases on either side, regardless of the presence of plasma. This behaviour is primarily attributed to the interplay between flame temperature and oxygen availability [21]. Consequently, the plasma enhancement of OH^* decreases with increasing equivalence ratio owing to the overall parabolic trend of OH^* intensity with the ϕ_g [23]. This may be one of the contributing factors to the observed increase in NO production around an ϕ_g of 0.8–0.85 for both plasma and no plasma conditions as shown in Fig. 7. In contrast, NH_2^* exhibits an increasing trend with increase in ϕ_g , regardless of the plasma actuation. However, the increase in NH_2^* is

significantly more pronounced under plasma conditions, primarily due to NH_3 decomposition via electron impact reactions [19]. Despite this, the NH_2^* intensity increases with nearly identical slopes in both plasma and no plasma cases, resulting in a relatively constant trend in NH_2^* enhancement across the tested range of ϕ_g . The plasma enhancement of NH^* remains constant of 54–45 % for ϕ_g from 0.8 to 0.93. This enhancement in the NH^* intensity provides evidence of modified chemical pathways under plasma influence ($\text{NH} + \text{NO} \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + \text{OH}$ and $\text{NH} + \text{NO} \rightarrow \text{N}_2\text{O} + \text{H}$) [40].

Interestingly OH^* intensity increases by 62 % at $\phi_g = 0.8$, it subsequently drops to 32 % at $\phi_g = 0.88$. However, NH_2^* intensity enhancement remains steady at 68–80 % across all tested ϕ_g values, potentially explaining the maximum NO reduction of 60 % at $\phi_g = 0.8$ without any NH_3 slip. This strategy of plasma-assisted combustion via fuel actuation could significantly enhance the production of NH_2 radical via electron impact reactions ($\text{NH}_3 + e \rightarrow \text{NH}_2 + \text{H} + e$), without promoting OH formation ($\text{NH}_3 + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{NH}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$) due to limited plasma interaction with air, unlike conventional premixed GAP combustor. The concentrations of NH_3 in the burned gases is negligible (<3 ppm) in the range of $\phi_g = 0.76$ –0.93, with noticeable NH_3 slip beyond this range. Beyond $\phi_g = 0.93$, NO concentrations are low probably due to NH_3 slip caused by incomplete combustion. This De- NO_x ing process is similar to the reduction by direct NH_3 injection into the combustor [41]. Observations of NH_3 slip above 0.93 and below 0.76, accompanied by negligible NO emissions, highlight the potential of employing axial combustion staging as a future technique to reduce NH_3 leakage without compromising NO_x mitigation. In addition, further analysis is needed to investigate the effects of different plasma conditions such as plasma power, frequency, and spatial location of plasma on NO_x formation and NH_3 slip. The increase in unburned NH_3 emissions with plasma actuation can be attributed to the increased NH_2 concentrations generated by the plasma via $2\text{NH}_2 \rightarrow \text{NH}_3 + \text{NH}$ and $\text{NH}_2 + \text{H} + \text{M} \rightarrow \text{NH}_3 + \text{M}$ routes [41]. The plasma-induced alteration of the reaction pathways, particularly under near-stoichiometric conditions where radical chemistry becomes significant. The NH_3 is ionised by plasma into a mixture of NH_3 , H_2 , NH_2 , and other species, primarily explaining the observed increase in NH_2 . However, plasma-induced thermal and hydrodynamic effects are also significant, which can alter operating conditions. Therefore, although the recombination reactions are strong near the stoichiometric condition, localised preheating and modified flow may create fuel-rich regions, limit the NH_3 -air interaction and allow NH_3 to escape [7]. The N_2O follows a conventional trend, with levels remaining near zero between $\phi_g = 0.84$ and 1.1, while increasing for leaner ϕ_g , regardless of plasma activation [4]. Note that for $\phi_g < 0.8$, without plasma, the flame cannot be sustained. This emission analysis reveals that a trade-off between NO and unburnt NH_3 emissions exist with plasma actuation suggests that there is an optimal lean equivalence ratio for minimising overall emissions in NH_3 -air combustion. Unlike the richer mixtures typically required for two-stage NH_3 -air combustion, plasma-assisted combustion presents the potential to simultaneously reduce both NO and unburnt NH_3 emissions under fuel-lean conditions.

To further investigate the mechanisms underlying NO mitigation by plasma, a detailed numerical study is conducted using coupled ZDPlaskin-Chemkin model. The simulations were performed for all lean conditions but only results for $\phi_g = 0.9$ are presented here for brevity.

The rate of production (ROP) analysis is conducted to examine the impact of plasma on NO formation and consumption mechanisms as shown in Fig. 9.

The analysis focuses on the ten most influential reactions governing NO production and consumption, with results normalised to the largest absolute reaction rate.

For the no plasma case, as identified in previous studies [4,7], NO is primarily produced via the HNO pathway, with key reactions including $\text{HNO} + \text{OH} \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{H} + \text{NO} (+\text{M}) \rightarrow \text{HNO} (+\text{M})$. The reduction of NO through reactions with NH_x species depends on environmental conditions that either promote or inhibit these pathways. Under plasma

Fig. 9. Rate of production of NO formation and consumption at $\phi_g = 0.9$.

conditions, thermal De-NO_x reactions are significantly enhanced, particularly through the chain-branching reaction $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} \rightarrow \text{NNH} + \text{OH}$ and the chain-termination reaction $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$. These reactions are crucial for predicting flame speed and NO_x formation. The dominance of the $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ pathway under plasma conditions aligns well with the experimentally observed increase in NH_2^* (Fig. 4). A detailed path flux analysis was conducted for NO at $\phi_g = 0.9$ which also complement the ROP analysis shown in Fig. S3 in the supplementary material. Further a detailed numerical simulation, incorporating a comprehensive chemical reaction network, are currently in progress to provide deeper insights into the NO reduction mechanisms.

Moreover, the NO mitigation performance of the present combustor is compared with a similar GAP from the literature [21–23] for an NH₃-air mixture, as shown in Fig. 10. The results indicate that the present combustor achieves a significantly higher NO_x reduction of 45–60 % while consuming a negligible power of just 1.4 %, compared to the literature. This highlights the capability of the present novel approach in mitigating NO_x emissions, even at equivalence ratios where NO_x peaks.

4. Conclusion

The impact of plasma on the stability and emission characteristics of a partially premixed pure NH₃-air flame is studied in the present study. The main findings are summarised below.

1. Various flame morphologies, from stable to tubular, were observed for different global equivalence ratios for the no-plasma cases. The plasma mitigated all flame instabilities and expanded the stable region by 35 % and 15–20 % for RBO and LBO, respectively. This is mainly due to the continuous local ignition through heating and generation of active species pools.
2. The plasma was found to have a strong influence on the pollutant emissions. NO and NO₂ were reduced by 40–80 % and 30–50 %, respectively, depending on the global equivalence ratio. These reductions were primarily attributed to the enhanced production of NH₂ radicals, which mitigated NO_x formation under plasma conditions. A significant NH₃ slip was observed beyond global equivalence ratio of 0.93 and 0.76, which was due to incomplete combustion at higher equivalence ratios.
3. The developed numerical model for the gliding arc plasma revealed that NO is primarily produced via the HNO pathway. Plasma conditions enhance thermal De-NO_x reactions, particularly through the chain-branching reaction $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} \rightarrow \text{NNH} + \text{OH}$ and the chain-termination reaction $\text{NH}_2 + \text{NO} \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

This study lays the groundwork for further investigations into the

Fig. 10. Comparison of plasma-enhanced NO mitigation in NH₃-air using gliding arc discharge ($\phi_g = 0.8$ – 0.9 selected for comparison).

impact of premixing levels and plasma on NO_x emissions, with ongoing simulations aimed at deepening the understanding of reduction mechanisms.

Novelty and significance statement

This study introduces a novel approach by applying plasma directly to the fuel stream in plasma-assisted swirl ammonia-air flames, facilitating immediate premixing after plasma interaction. This study bridges the gap in plasma-assisted ammonia combustion by simultaneously enhancing flame stability and reducing NO_x emissions. It is the first to focus on generating NH₂ radicals through plasma actuation while maintaining OH production, thereby promoting the De-NO_x pathway and significantly decreasing NO_x emissions. Additionally, the present combustor achieves 45–60 % reduction in NO_x emissions while consuming only 1.4 % of the power compared to existing literature. This underscores the effectiveness of our novel approach in mitigating NO_x emissions, even under conditions where generally NO_x peaks.

Author contributions

BA designed research, performed research, analysed data, and wrote the paper. ZW analysed data and revised the paper. SM Analysed data and revised the paper. DL analysed data and revised the paper. AV secured the funding, designed research, and revised the paper.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in

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References

- [1] A. Valera-Medina, H. Xiao, M. Owen-Jones, W.I. David, P. Bowen, Ammonia for power, *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* 69 (2018) 63–102.
- [2] H. Kobayashi, A. Hayakawa, K.K.A. Somaratne, E.C. Okafor, Science and technology of ammonia combustion, *Proceedings of the combustion institute*, 37 (2019) 109–133.
- [3] A.M. Elbaz, S. Wang, T.F. Guiberti, W.L. Roberts, Review on the recent advances on ammonia combustion from the fundamentals to the applications, *Fuel Communications* 10 (2022) 100053.
- [4] S. Mashruk, H. Shi, L. Mazzotta, C.E. Ustun, B. Aravind, R. Meloni, A. Alnasif, E. Boulet, R. Jankowski, C. Yu, Perspectives on NO_x emissions and impacts from Ammonia combustion processes, *Energy Fuels* 38 (2024) 19253–19292.
- [5] H. Xiao, A. Valera-Medina, P.J. Bowen, Study on premixed combustion characteristics of co-firing ammonia/methane fuels, *Energy* 140 (2017) 125–135.
- [6] M. Srinivasarao, G. Sorrentino, M. de Joannon, V.M. Reddy, Pure ammonia flames with high thermal intensities through fuel and air staging under extreme rich-to-lean conditions, *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute*, 40 (2024) 105241.
- [7] S. Mashruk, H. Xiao, A. Valera-Medina, Rich-Quench-lean model comparison for the clean use of humidified ammonia/hydrogen combustion systems, *Int. J. Hydrogen. Energy* 46 (2021) 4472–4484.
- [8] N.N. Shohdy, M. Alicherif, T.F. Guiberti, E.-t. Es-sebbar, D.A. Lacoste, Quantitative comparison of the benefits of cracking and nanosecond repetitive pulsed discharges on the lean blow-off, emissions, and topology of ammonia premixed swirl flames, *Combust. Flame* 269 (2024) 113678.
- [9] D.A. Lacoste, Flames with plasmas, *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute*, 39 (2023) 5405–5428.
- [10] Y. Ju, W. Sun, Plasma assisted combustion: dynamics and chemistry, *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* 48 (2015) 21–83.
- [11] Y. Ju, W. Sun, Plasma assisted combustion: progress, challenges, and opportunities, *Combust. Flame* 162 (2015) 529–532.
- [12] A. Shioyoke, J. Hayashi, R. Murai, N. Nakatsuka, F. Akamatsu, Numerical investigation on effects of nonequilibrium plasma on laminar burning velocity of ammonia flame, *Energy Fuels* 32 (2018) 3824–3832.
- [13] G.T. Kim, J. Park, S.H. Chung, C.S. Yoo, Effects of non-thermal plasma on turbulent premixed flames of ammonia/air in a swirl combustor, *Fuel* 323 (2022) 124227.
- [14] G. Faingold, J.K. Lefkowitz, A numerical investigation of NH₃/O₂/He ignition limits in a non-thermal plasma, *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute*, 38 (2021) 6661–6669.
- [15] M. Shahsavari, A.A. Konnov, A. Valera-Medina, M. Jangi, On nanosecond plasma-assisted ammonia combustion: effects of pulse and mixture properties, *Combust. Flame* 245 (2022) 112368.
- [16] J. Choe, W. Sun, T. Ombrello, C. Carter, Plasma assisted ammonia combustion: simultaneous NO_x reduction and flame enhancement, *Combust. Flame* 228 (2021) 430–432.
- [17] T.S. Taneja, P.N. Johnson, S. Yang, Nanosecond pulsed plasma assisted combustion of ammonia-air mixtures: effects on ignition delays and NO_x emission, *Combust. Flame* 245 (2022) 112327.
- [18] Z.A. Shah, G. Mehdi, P.M. Congedo, D. Mazzeo, M.G. De Giorgi, A review of recent studies and emerging trends in plasma-assisted combustion of ammonia as an effective hydrogen carrier, *Int. J. Hydrogen. Energy* 51 (2024) 354–374.
- [19] A.M. Radwan, M.C. Paul, Plasma assisted NH₃ combustion and NO_x reduction technologies: principles, challenges and prospective, *Int. J. Hydrogen. Energy* 52 (2024) 819–833.
- [20] D. Lee, K.-T. Kim, M. Cha, Y.-H. Song, Optimization scheme of a rotating gliding arc reactor for partial oxidation of methane, *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute*, 31 (2007) 3343–3351.
- [21] Y. Tang, D. Xie, B. Shi, N. Wang, S. Li, Flammability enhancement of swirling ammonia/air combustion using AC powered gliding arc discharges, *Fuel* 313 (2022) 122674.
- [22] J. Sun, Q. Huang, Y. Tang, S. Li, Stabilization and emission characteristics of gliding arc-assisted NH₃/CH₄/air premixed flames in a swirl combustor, *Energy Fuels* 36 (2022) 8520–8527.
- [23] R. Ju, J. Wang, M. Zhang, H. Mu, G. Zhang, J. Yu, Z. Huang, Stability and emission characteristics of ammonia/air premixed swirling flames with rotating gliding arc discharge plasma, *Energy* 277 (2023) 127649.
- [24] X. Zhang, S.P. Moosakutty, R.P. Rajan, M. Younes, S.M. Sarathy, Combustion chemistry of ammonia/hydrogen mixtures: jet-stirred reactor measurements and comprehensive kinetic modeling, *Combust. Flame* 234 (2021) 111653.
- [25] S. Wang, X. Wei, M. Gu, Q. Lin, G. Luo, F. Hu, Flame characteristics and NO emission law of sliding arc plasma-assisted ammonia combustion, *Combust. Flame* 274 (2025) 114000.
- [26] Q. Lin, Y. Jiang, C. Liu, L. Chen, W. Zhang, J. Ding, J. Li, Controllable NO emission and high flame performance of ammonia combustion assisted by non-equilibrium plasma, *Fuel* 319 (2022) 123818.
- [27] A. Gaydon, *The Spectroscopy of Flames*, Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [28] B.S. ISO, Gas turbines exhaust Gas emission measurement and evaluation British Standards Institution U.K, (1996) 11042.
- [29] X. Mao, H. Zhong, N. Liu, Z. Wang, Y. Ju, Ignition enhancement and NO_x formation of NH₃/air mixtures by non-equilibrium plasma discharge, *Combust. Flame* 259 (2024) 113140.
- [30] H. Zhong, X. Mao, N. Liu, Z. Wang, T. Ombrello, Y. Ju, Understanding non-equilibrium N₂O/NO_x chemistry in plasma-assisted low-temperature NH₃ oxidation, *Combust. Flame* 256 (2023) 112948.
- [31] L.W. Crispim, P.H. Hallak, M.S. Benilov, M.Y. Ballester, Modelling spark-plug discharge in dry air, *Combust. Flame* 198 (2018) 81–88.
- [32] G. Dong, Y. Zhou, P. Ming, Z. Wu, H. Chen, Y. Huang, L. Li, Kinetics-based analysis of the gliding arc plasma assisted ammonia decomposition process towards vehicle on-board applications, *Chem. Eng. J.* 505 (2025) 159443.
- [33] J. J. A. Alnasif, M. Papp, A.G. Szanthoffer, M. Kovaleva, T. Turanyi, A. Valera Medina, T. Nagy, Compact kinetic model for the combustion of NH₃/H₂ mixtures, Submitted to *J. Ammonia Energy* - (2025). -.
- [34] X. Zhu, A.A. Khateeb, T.F. Guiberti, W.L. Roberts, NO and OH* emission characteristics of very-lean to stoichiometric ammonia–hydrogen–air swirl flames, *Proceedings of the combustion institute*, 38 (2021) 5155–5162.
- [35] A. Hayakawa, Y. Arakawa, R. Mimoto, K.K.A. Somaratne, T. Kudo, H. Kobayashi, Experimental investigation of stabilization and emission characteristics of ammonia/air premixed flames in a swirl combustor, *Int. J. Hydrogen. Energy* 42 (2017) 14010–14018.
- [36] F. Zhang, G. Zhang, Z. Wang, D. Wu, M. Jangi, H. Xu, Experimental investigation on combustion and emission characteristics of non-premixed ammonia/hydrogen flame, *Int. J. Hydrogen. Energy* 61 (2024) 25–38.
- [37] S.J. Shanhogue, S. Husain, T. Lieuwen, Lean blowoff of bluff body stabilized flames: scaling and dynamics, *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* 35 (2009) 98–120.
- [38] Q. Zhang, D.R. Noble, T. Lieuwen, Characterization of fuel composition effects in H₂/CO/CH₄ mixtures upon lean blowout, (2007).
- [39] S. Mashruk, E.C. Okafor, M. Kovaleva, A. Alnasif, D. Pugh, A. Hayakawa, A. Valera-Medina, Evolution of N₂O production at lean combustion condition in NH₃/H₂/air premixed swirling flames, *Combust. Flame* 244 (2022) 112299.
- [40] H. Tang, S. Gubbi, W. Sun, Investigation of flame structure in plasma-assisted ammonia swirling flames using NH planar laser-induced fluorescence, *Combust. Flame* 274 (2025) 114006.
- [41] D. Pugh, P. Bowen, A. Valera-Medina, A. Giles, J. Runyon, R. Marsh, Influence of steam addition and elevated ambient conditions on NO_x reduction in a staged premixed swirling NH₃/H₂ flame, *Proceedings of the combustion institute*, 37 (2019) 5401–5409.